

ELABORATING PRINTING PARAMETERS IN USING INKJET PRINTING TO TOUGHEN CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Inkjet printing has been used to deposit poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) as toughening materials between laminate plies before curing stage. The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) and apparent interlaminar shear strength (aILSS) were measured by means of double cantilever beam (DCB) and short beam shear (SBS) test. Different patterns were designed for patterning PMMA deposits into carbon fibre reinforced composites to investigate their potential effect on the mechanical performances of printed laminates. The results showed that laminates with printed PMMA deposits hexagonally patterned had an maximum 40% improvement in $G_{Ic(\text{propagation})}$ while retaining the aILSS compared to the non-printed (NP) control. The system with printed PMMA-PEG dual materials showed a similar toughening efficiency to the one with printed PMMA only. Continuous phase (film) of PMMA enhanced the G_{Ic} of printed laminates at the expense of aILSS. Optical microscopy was used to study the morphology of polymer deposits embedded in epoxy resin. The geometrical and dimensional distribution of polymer deposits were assumed as the main factors to explain the observed mechanical performances.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites have made a remarkable breakthrough in areas such as aeronautical, automotive, electrical and architectural engineering due to their desirable properties such as high stiffness-weight and strength-weight ratios, low coefficient of thermal expansion and high corrosion resistance compared to traditional metallic materials [1]. However, composite laminates are susceptible to delamination because lack of reinforcement in through thickness direction, which limits its effective applications. Delamination is considered as the most critical failure mode of this material, it develops from microcracks which could be generated from manufacturing defects or in-service damages [2-4]. Unfortunately, these microcracks are difficult to detect at their early stage, but can result in catastrophic failure later on [5, 6], thus it is of great importance to improve the resistance to delamination of laminated composites.

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) is one of the parameters used to evaluate the capability of composite laminates to resist delamination growth. Researchers demonstrated that the interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRPs laminates can be significantly enhanced by using various interleaves such as thermoplastic films [7, 8] and carbon nanofiber/nanotube [9, 10]. This method places interleaves between laminate plies to co-cure with prepreg into laminates, the interleaves ideally remain as a discrete toughened layer between laminas after curing to achieve an effective toughening [2, 11]. However, this interleaving method may compromise some mechanical performances of toughened laminates, such as interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) [12, 13]. Also, the additional interleaves unavoidably increase the thickness and weight of final laminates, which may well be a problem for applications in industry.

Drop-on-demand (DOD) inkjet printing is an attractive technique which can generate uniform droplets in picolitre volume range and precisely dispense those droplets directly into pre-designed

patterns without masks [14, 15]. The major advantages of using inkjet printing to create features are as following: 1) ease of changing pre-designed patterns with assistance of computer; 2) efficient material usage as droplets are printed only at places where needed; 3) capability of precisely dispensing droplets enable it can be applied to fabricate delicate structures; 4) minimised potential contaminations in final products as its non-contact fabrication process. Take the above advantages of using inkjet printing, this technique has been used in a variety of applications such as fabricating scaffolds for tissue engineering [16], printing electronics [17], delivery of biological factors [18-20] and toughening composite laminates [21, 22]. Recently, it has been reported that inkjet printing was used to introduce an organic system which possesses self-healing capability into CFRP composite [23]. The G_{Ic} of crack propagation and aILSS (apparent ILSS) was increased by 27% and 11% respectively compared to the non-printed controls (Fig. 1A). The tested samples for measuring aILSS then went through a heat treatment to trigger the thermally activated self-healing, and showed less deterioration in properties compared to the controls (Fig. 1B).

Figure 1: A) Comparisons of ILSS between printed samples and unprinted controls before and after thermal treatment. B) Comparisons of reduction in average aILSS between printed samples and unprinted controls [23].

Since delamination tends to occur at the interface between laminate plies [6], and considering the aforementioned penalties by using interleaves, discrete polymer deposits instead of interleave were printed onto prepreg by inkjet printing before curing into composites. Previous work [21] showed that poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) micro-sized deposits were respectively printed onto prepreg with controllable pattern dimensions before curing, and the G_{Ic} (both initiation and propagation) of PMMA containing CFRP laminates was enhanced while aILSS was maintained. As inkjet printing is capable of designing and changing between printing patterns flexibly, investigation into the effect of different printing patterns on mechanical properties of final CFRP laminates is of great interest to investigate further. Also, PMMA and PEG were alternatively printed onto prepreg before curing thanks to the capability of the multi-nozzle equipped printer, which allowed the dual-material toughening system to be studied. Mechanical properties of polymer printed CFRP laminates were tested by means of double cantilever beam (DCB) and short beam shear (SBS) to determine the G_{Ic} and aILSS respectively.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

1.1 Solution preparation for inkjet printing

PMMA ($M_w \sim 15$ kDa) and PEG ($M_n \sim 20$ kDa) were dissolved in N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and deionised water with different weight percentage respectively to form the solutions for printing. Table 1 shows the viscosity and surface tension of the prepared solutions. All measured viscosities and surface tensions suggested that these solutions should be suitable for inkjet printing [24]. All chemicals

were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich Co. Ltd., UK) and used as received. Viscosity and surface tension were measured at room temperature using an A&D sine-wave vibro viscometer (European Instruments, UK) and KRÜSS K11 tensiometer (KRÜSS GmbH, Hamburg, Germany) respectively.

Solution	wt%	Viscosity / mPa·s	Surface tension / mN m ⁻¹
PMMA	10	2.05	36.43
PMMA	20	6.32	36.46
PEG	10	18.5	58.20

Table 1: Viscosity and surface tension of PMMA and PEG solutions.

1.2 Patterns for printing

A drop-on-demand (DOD) JetLab 4xl printer equipped with a compatible MicroJet printhead (orifice diameter: 60 μm) was employed as the deposition tool (MicroFab Inc. Plano, USA). As the DCB test aims at a specific interface, only the mid-thickness ply was printed with polymer deposits. For the SBS test, every interface between laminate plies was printed with polymer.

Our previous research showed that increasing the amount of PMMA deposits between laminate plies led to an increase in $G_{Ic(\text{initiation})}$ and $G_{Ic(\text{propagation})}$, up to about 40% [25]. In this work, different discrete dot and line patterns and continuous phase (film) were employed to investigate their potential effect on the G_{Ic} of the printed laminates. Since the previous experiments showed that samples prepared using 10 wt% PMMA solution performed the best among the groups in terms of material usage efficiency, it was chosen as the main printing solution. Four different patterns which have the same amount of material usage per unit printed area were designed for printing as shown in Figure 2. Parameters dx is dots spacing in x axis direction and dy is dots spacing in y axis direction, both can be verified to change the shape and density of patterns. 10 wt% PMMA and 10 wt% PEG solutions were used to alternatively print deposits patterned in hexagon as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Different printing patterns for printing.

Figure 3: Alternatively printed hexagon pattern ($dx/dy = 0.4/0.2$ mm) using PMMA and PEG solutions.

In order to investigate the effect of using discrete dot pattern and continuous phase (film) on the mechanical properties of final laminates, 20 wt% PMMA solution was used to print hexagon and film at specific ply respectively. The reason of using a higher percentage of PMMA solution was to generate a thicker continuous phase as much as possible, because the volume of jetted droplet was too small, the thickness of printed film was calculated about 2 μm .

1.3 Sample fabrication

Unidirectional CFRP prepreg tape (CYCOM[®]977-2, Cytec Industries Inc., USA) was used to fabricate CFRP laminates. 12 (DCB) and 8 (SBS) printed plies of prepreg were laid-up unidirectionally for subsequent curing into laminates respectively. A non-stick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film was inserted at the mid-thickness ply of DCB panel to simulate a crack to allow the crack propagation at the interested interface. A customised autoclave (Premier Autoclaves Ltd., UK) was used to consolidate the laid-up panels. For the detailed curing cycles please refer to our previous work [22]. DCB and SBS samples were cut into $140 \pm 1 \text{ mm} \times 20 \pm 0.5 \text{ mm} \times 3 \pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$ and $20 \pm 1 \text{ mm} \times 10 \pm 0.2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \pm 0.2 \text{ mm}$ in accordance with the test standards [26, 27]. Two 11.9 mm 11.9 mm centre-drilled metal blocks were bonded to each PTFE inserted DCB samples ends for fitting into the test machine. For improving the visibility of the crack propagation, the edges of DCB test samples were painted with a white correction fluid.

1.4 Test procedures

A tensometer (TA500 Texture Analyser, Lloyd Instruments, UK) equipped with a 500N load cell was used to conduct the DCB test in tension mode. The speed of crosshead was 5 mm/min. The test samples were first precracked using a mode I opening load to avoid any resin rich pockets and generate a sharp crack tip for subsequent test. A high definition camcorder was used to record the DCB test for determining the delamination length for data reduction. Figure 4 schematically shows the DCB test configuration.

Figure 4: Configuration of DCB test.

The short beam shear test was carried out using a benchtop tester (H25KS, Tinius Olsen Ltd., UK) equipped with a 25KN load cell in three-point compression mode. The speed of crosshead was 1 mm/min. The span/thickness ratio was 5 which is recommended by the test standard. Figure 5 schematically shows the SBS test configuration.

Figure 5: Configuration of SBS test.

1.5 Preparation of epoxy coated glass slides with printed polymer deposits

In order to understand the morphology of printed polymer deposits embedded in epoxy resin after curing, microscope glass slides were coated with a layer of an epoxy resin (CYCOM[®]977-20 RTM, Cytec Engineered Materials Ltd., UK) followed by a precure to mimic the resin state in the prepreg for a good visibility. The precured glass slides then were used as the substrate with PMMA and PEG deposits printed on, the printed glass slides were dried at room temperature for at least 1 hour before covering with another precured epoxy coated glass slide followed by the heat treatment (160°C for 30 min). Optical images were taken at two stages: before heating (without covering another coated glass slide) and after heating.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Variation in patterns

It can be seen from Figure 6 that all the four groups with printed PMMA deposits had improved $G_{Ic}(\text{initiation})$ and $G_{Ic}(\text{propagation})$, up to 40% compared to the non-printed (NP) control as expected. Especially, samples with printed hexagon (pattern 4) showed the highest improved G_{Ic} corresponding to both crack initiation and propagation. Although these four patterns have the same PMMA usage per unit area, the surface coverage of PMMA (which is the area covered by printed PMMA deposits divided by the unit area) varies due to the overlapping of PMMA deposits in line pattern. The surface coverage of pattern 1 and 2 was about 24%, while pattern 3 and 4 have an approximately 37% surface coverage. Therefore, the less PMMA covered areas (line pattern) was assumed as the reason to explain the lower resistance to delamination.

Figure 6: G_{Ic} comparison between NP and samples with printed different patterns (error bars represent standard deviation, $n = 5$).

3.2 Effect of printed film on crack propagation

It can be seen from Figure 7 that the average $G_{Ic(\text{initiation})}$ and $G_{Ic(\text{propagation})}$ of film group were higher than that of discrete dot system. However, the crack propagations of samples with printed PMMA film were unstable compared to that of samples with printed discrete PMMA dots and NP, which is not ideal for applications in industry. Although the surface coverage of PMMA in film system was 100%, significantly higher than that of the discrete dot pattern, and the PMMA usage was 8 times as much as discrete dot system, the toughening efficiency was not as higher as the increase in material usage. These results illustrate the advantage of depositing discrete dot pattern instead of film in terms of material usage efficiency. The aLSS of film group decreased by 5.5% compared to the control. However, samples in hexagon pattern group preserved the interlaminar strength compared to the control. Moreover, the standard deviations of G_{Ic} and aLSS were dramatically larger than the other groups, indicating the inhomogeneity of the film printed samples.

Figure 7: G_{Ic} , aLSS and crack propagation comparisons between NP and PMMA printed ($n = 5$).

3.3 Dual-material toughening

Although using polymers as toughening materials to optimise brittle epoxy has received extensive attention, the systems were mainly focused on using a single toughening material. Therefore, it is of interest to know whether introducing two toughening materials simultaneously would bring any positive effect on the mechanical properties to optimise the mechanical integrity of toughened laminates. Figure 8 shows the dual-material system had a similar toughening efficiency compared to that of the single material system (PMMA), while the interlaminar strength of dual-material system seemed the best among the three groups.

Figure 8: G_{1c} and aLSS comparisons between NP, PMMA and PMMA+PEG printed.

3.4 Morphology of PMMA and PEG deposits

Figure 9(b) shows the PMMA deposits patterned in hexagons after heating formed micro-sized particles embedded in the epoxy resin while retaining the printed pattern. The size of the pattern after heating expanded to a small amount due to the ‘flowability’ of the resin during heating. The diameter of the PMMA particles was about 37 μm , and varied in a small range. However, the printed continuous phase broke down into randomly distributed particles with a wide range of diameter as shown in Figure 9(d). The printed PMMA lines also broke down into particles with a random size, but they were still patterned in lines as shown in Figure 9(f).

Figure 9: Morphology of PMMA deposits embedded in epoxy resin. (a,c,e) before heating; (b,d,f) after heating.

Unlike the PMMA, PEG deposits had a good miscibility with the epoxy resin as there was no distinguished particles formed after heating. The printed pattern still can be identified after heating (Fig. 10(b)), suggesting the PEG did not completely diffuse into the whole resin, but formed PEG dissolved epoxy regions.

Figure 10: Morphology of PEG deposits embedded in epoxy resin. (a) before heating; (b) after heating.

3.5 Discussion

The toughening of PMMA printed CFRP laminates is likely attributed to the geometrical effect of thermoplastic zones and the deformation of ductile thermoplastic zones which can dissipate energy. The discrete dot pattern system had an evenly distribution of PMMA particles, and the size of particles was controllable, thus, the crack tips encountered those size-similar zones regularly, resulting in a relatively stable crack propagation. However, the unstable crack propagation (Fig. 7) of film system was because of the uncontrollable distribution and size of PMMA particles, the crack tips encountered the plastic zones with randomness in both distribution and size. The reason for the best improved G_{Ic} (initiation and propagation) of hexagon pattern group as shown in Figure 6 could be attributed to the complexity of deposit locations. The crack path could be more diverted by the hexagon pattern compared to line and rectangle. Figure 11 schematically shows the possible crack propagation. However, a detailed information about the crack path should be investigated further.

Figure 11: Schematically show the diverted crack paths by different patterns.

The noticeable decrease in aILSS of samples with printed film was likely attributed to the excessive presence of PMMA phases. The large standard deviation observed in Figure 7 indicated that the poor controllability of the PMMA particles formation in both distribution and size inside the laminate samples (Fig. 9). The evenly distributed PMMA particles with consistent size seemed barely affect the interlaminar strength of printed laminates, suggesting the geometrical and size distribution of toughening material at the interface between laminate plies have a critical effect on the mechanical properties of toughened laminate composites.

In the dual-material system, PEG dissolved epoxy regions and PMMA particles would have a combined toughening mechanism, although it is not well understood at the present time. The flexibility of PEG chains, the crystallisation of PEG and the areas around PMMA particles could be the main aspects and form the focus of future work.

4 CONCLUSION

Different patterns for inkjet printing of PMMA solutions were collaborated with CFRP composites. Samples with printed PMMA deposits patterned in hexagon pattern had an maximum 40% increase in $G_{Ic(\text{propagation})}$ while retaining the aILSS compared to the control. Although samples with printing PMMA film showed the highest improvement in both $G_{Ic(\text{initiation})}$ and $G_{Ic(\text{propagation})}$, the crack growth was unstable and the aILSS was sacrificed, indicating the necessity of using a discrete dot pattern. Using a dual-material toughening system showed a similar toughening effectiveness compared to that of system with printed PMMA only, and the aILSS seemed increased slightly. The evenly distributed PMMA particles with a constant size were assumed as the reasons to explain the stable crack propagation. It was postulated that the plastic deformation of PMMA particles dissipated the energy, which resulted in the improvement of fracture toughness.

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